

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D2.1 Accessible map of ecosystems, reporting on clusters' needs, capabilities and barriers to procurement of innovation

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PROCEDIN

Procurement Capability - Embedding and Driving Innovation

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1 Introduction

The purpose of Task 2.1 is to identify and outline the entities to be activated and engaged in PROCEDIN endeavours, with the intention of fostering linkages and networks between procurers and providers. Specifically, it is about mapping and engaging stakeholders representing all groups relevant to procurement of innovation (POI), ensuring the active participation of public and private buyers with the willingness to purchase innovations, and of organisations which support them and form part of the innovation ecosystem. It is closely linked to T2.3, to facilitate procurement leadership in driving and embedding POI to generate dynamic innovation ecosystems. Together, these two tasks and other PROCEDIN activities mobilise key POI stakeholders to accelerate and embed POI adoption.

Relevant stakeholders are identified and clustered (by type, interest, geographical dimension, etc.). Another aim of this task is to pinpoint and engage additional entities with the potential to support and offer expert guidance during the POI process. These connections will aid in the creation of fresh partnerships and consortia among providers, fostering knowledge exchange and collective involvement in PPIs. This undertaking will receive backing from other related projects and initiatives carried out within the framework of the Innovation Procurement Task Force.

The leadership role for this task is assumed by PEDAL, with support from contributing partners, namely HAA, F6S, GAB and UT.

2 PROCEDIN Stakeholder scouting and mapping methodology

2.1 Categories and criteria assessment

i. Assessing the stakeholders categories

The stakeholders have been segmented into the following four clusters, accounting for their roles in the realm of innovative procurement:

1. *Entities involved in the procurement of innovation, termed as "Innovation demand"*: This grouping pertains to organizations or individuals, hailing from either the public or private domain, who express a requirement or desire for novel products, services, or solutions. They represent potential customers seeking innovative resolutions for particular challenges or specific needs.
2. *SMEs, startups, spin-offs, universities, incubators, and technology centers, referred to as "Innovation supply"*: These entities constitute the essential components of the innovation ecosystem, contributing to the creation and provision of inventive products, services, or solutions. Their involvement often spans research, development, and the commercialization of fresh technologies or concepts.
3. *Other pertinent contributors: Intermediaries, Advocacy groups, Associations, Consultants, Policy Formulators, termed as "Multipliers"*. This category encompasses a diverse array of stakeholders who play a pivotal role in facilitating and bolstering innovation-related activities. Their interests might encompass both those of innovation suppliers and innovation demanders.
4. *Initiatives linked to Innovative Procurement, labeled as "Projects"*: This classification pertains to specific undertakings or ventures centered around innovative procurement. Activities within this category could encompass the formulation of procurement strategies, execution of market analyses, specification delineation, supervision of procurement processes, training in POI, and evaluation of the impact stemming from initiatives tied to innovative procurement.

ii. Identification of clustering criteria

For every category of stakeholder the name of the organization, website details, geographic particulars (city, country), and secured information (email, phone, name), were collated. Personal information encompasses data associated with contacts who have granted consent or have been openly shared (for example on a public webpage), and therefore PROCEDIN data complies with the regulations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To assess a particular stakeholder's probable engagement level, knowledge of their past collaborative interactions, along with potential interest and incentive concerning PROCEDIN tasks, were considered.

Distinct criteria were formulated for every individual category.

1. Innovation Demand

Criteria	Options	Definition
----------	---------	------------

Innovation Demand	Individual Public Buyer	
	Central Purchasing body	
	Regional Purchasing body	
	Private Purchasing body(not direct target)	
	Other	
Level of activity	City level	
	Regional	
	Transregional	
	National	
	EU	
	International	
	N/A	
NUTS 2021 classification	NUTS 1	Major socio-economic regions
	NUTS 2	Basic regions for the application of regional policies
	NUTS 3	Small region for specific diagnoses
Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation	Small	Up to 10% of the annual budget
	Medium	Up to 25% of the annual budget
	Large	More than 25% of the annual budget

Table 1 -. Clustering criteria for Innovation Demand

2. Innovation Supply

Application field of their innovation relevant for PROCEDIN:

- Green mobility
- Circular economy

3. Multipliers

Multiplier stakeholder type:

Criteria	Options
Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intermediary • National centre for public administration training • Industrial cluster • Investor/alternative financing • Associations/lobby • Advisors/consultancy/legal • Policy maker • Trade union/civil society • European institution • Media • Other

Level of Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City level • Regional • Transregional • National • International • EU • N/A
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Table 2 - Clustering criteria for Multipliers

4. Projects

Criteria	Options
Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing • Concluded
Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green mobility • Circular Economy
Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) • Pre Commercial Procurement (PCP) • Public Procurement (PP) • Green Public Procurement (GPP) • Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP)
Programme	
Start and end date	
Coordinator	
Coordinator country	
Projects assets and links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports • Tools • Events to be exploited

Table 3 - Clustering criteria for Projects

2.2 Creation of the database

After outlining the criteria, a collaborative spreadsheet was generated, encompassing all the details outlined in points (i) Assessing stakeholders categories and (ii) identification of clustering criteria. The rationale behind utilizing this tool is associated with the requirement for an online shared document, enabling all PROCEDIN project partners to input information and engage in the mapping and scouting endeavor. Any PROCEDIN project partner contributing stakeholder contacts to the spreadsheet was requested to endorse their role as a "Responsible partner" within the designated field, thereby serving as a primary point of contact. To conveniently and swiftly evaluate stakeholder engagements, a brief description of their involvement was provided in the designated section.

The comprehensive configuration of the database is presented in section 3.

2.3 Analysis and collection of stakeholders details through an online research

The research was performed using mainly the PROCEDIN partners' networks or resources found while performing their professional activities (i.e. academic research activity, web research, information

gathering etc.). No single or particular databases or platforms were used to gather the present results, therefore the search was wide ranging.

3 PROCEDIN Database

The database was established using a collaborative spreadsheet file. The details for each category were accumulated within their corresponding sheet. Alongside this, the spreadsheet incorporates guidelines for populating the pertinent details, to guarantee all PROCEDIN project partners possess a clear grasp of the process and to facilitate effective coordinated efforts, as shown in the screenshots below. The database entries followed the directives outlined in points (i) and (ii), assessing the stakeholders’ clusters and their categorisation criteria. Serving as an internal operational document, it was stored within the shared repository of the PROCEDIN project folder in Microsoft Teams, ensuring unrestricted access for all project partners. The information provided in this activity was used to create an interactive map of stakeholders which is available on the PROCEDIN website. Further details are available in section 4, “Results”.

	A	B
1	PROCEDIN Stakeholders mapping template: Instructions	
2		
3	Step1 (Drop down menus with groups identification)	
4		<i>Please read all the categories and subcategories in drop down menus. You are most welcome to identify a new stakeholder group and / or subgroup. In this case, please include your addition(s) in the respective fields.</i>
5		
6	Step2 (Main Template)	
7	4 sheets	<i>Please provide information for all the stakeholders. Stakeholders could be organisations, communities, individuals or related project. Please fill in all required fields according to the guidelines provided below:</i>
8	Stakeholder type	There are four main categories of stakeholders - 1 sheet - Innovation Demand, 2 sheet - Innovation Supply, 3 sheet - Multipliers + Other, 4 sheet Projects/Initiatives. As a first step, please choose under which one your information will go.
9	Level of activity	Choose the type from the drop down menu
10	NUTS 2021 classification	Choose if they are active on national/international/EU, etc level based on the drop down menu
11	PROCEDIN Partner name	NUTS 2021 is the Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics - hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK for the purpose of the collection, development and harmonisation of European regional statistics and socio-economic analyses of the regions.
12	Stakeholder/Organisation name	The name of your organisation (drop down menu)
13	Organisation details	The stakeholder’s organisation name
14	Contact details	Fill in all the details that you can - website, town, country, info on collaboration history, if any
15	Potential interest and motivation	Please keep in mind GDPR and include information only from people that we received consent to be contacted/included, etc for some activities (such as form surveys) and contact that are publicly available.
16	Projects	Include information for which Tasks/activities the stakeholder/organisation could be interested. What the stakeholder could most likely contribute to? What does PROCEDIN need from this stakeholder?
17	Projects - Relevant for collaboration	Include as much information as you can, including the general information if the project is ongoing (O) or concluded (C), project’s website, cordis’website, acronym and full project name, its area and any specific information to determine possible synergies and/or use of resources
18	Comments	Please rate yes, no, maybe
19		Add any comment that can be valuable for this stakeholder
20	Sheet: Categories	<i>IMPORTANT: Please do not edit this sheet</i>

Figure 1 - Instructions

Type					Responsible partner
Innovation Demand stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	NUTS 2021 classification	Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation (if available)	Short description* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in PROCEDIN)	PROCEDIN partner * (main contact)

Organisation name*	Website*	Town*	Country*	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)	
Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publicly shared)					
e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name		
T2.2. Call for Expression of Interest (M4-12)	T2.3 Identify procurement leaders' key barriers and enablers for embedding POI (M2-14)	T3.1 Develop legal framework materials (M9-12)	T3.2 Provide legal assistance (M12-18)	T3.3 Deliver legal assistance trainings (M12-18)	T3.4 Set up support arrangements for tools and best practices (M12-23)
T4.2 Promote University engagement (M7-21)	T4.3 Select and customise resource (M9-20)	T5.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities (M1-24)	T5.2 Liaison with existing networks and initiatives (M1-24)	Other (specify)	

Figure 2 - Innovation Demand sheet, all data categories

Type			Responsible partner		
Innovation Supply stakeholder type*	Application field of their innovation relevant for PROCEDIN*	Short description of the innovation proposed* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in PROCEDIN)	PROCEDIN partner*	Organisation name*	
Shared Contact Data					
Organisation name*	Website*	Town*	Country*	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)	
Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publicly shared)					
e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name		
T2.2. Call for Expression of Interest (M4-12)	T2.3 Identify procurement leaders' key barriers and enablers for embedding POI (M2-14)	T3.1 Develop legal framework materials (M9-12)	T3.2 Provide legal assistance (M12-18)	T3.3 Deliver legal assistance trainings (M12-18)	T3.4 Set up support arrangements for tools and best practices (M12-23)
T4.2 Promote University engagement (M7-21)	T4.3 Select and customise resource (M9-20)	T5.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities (M1-24)	T5.2 Liaison with existing networks and initiatives (M1-24)	Other (specify)	

Figure 3 - Innovation Supply sheet, all data categories

Type				Responsible partner
Multiplier stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	Short description of their activity*	Why relevant for PROCEDIN* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in PROCEDIN)	PROCEDIN partner*

Shared Contact Data					
Organisation name*	Website*	Town*	Country*	Registration in Tenderio (Y/N)	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)
Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publically shared)					
e-mail		other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name	
T2.2. Call for Expression of Interest (M4-12)	T2.3 Identify procurement leaders’ key barriers and enablers for embedding POI (M2-14)	T3.1 Develop legal framework materials (M9-12)	T3.2 Provide legal assistance (M12-18)	T3.3 Deliver legal assistance trainings (M12-18)	T3.4 Set up support arrangements for tools and best practices (M12-23)
T4.2 Promote University engagement (M7-21)		T4.3 Select and customise resource (M9-20)	T5.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities (M1-24)	T5.2 Liaison with existing networks and initiatives (M1-24)	Other (specify)

Figure 4 - Multipliers sheet, all data categories

Project Title					
Ongoing/C oncluded O/C	Relevant for collaboration Y/N/M (Maybe)	Project Acronym	Full name	Area	Domain
Type	website	Website (cordis)	Programme	Start date	End date
Coordinator		Country	project focus		
Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publically shared)					
e-mail		other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name	
Project's assets			Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)		Notes
Interesting Assets (reports, guidelines, tools, events, etc.) to be exploited		description and links to assets			

Figure 5 - Projects sheet, all data categories

4 Results

The mapping & scouting activity registered a total number of 204 stakeholders so far. Below it is represented the percentage for each category:

Category	Percentage
Innovation Demand	13.4%
Innovation Supply	67.1%
Multipliers	10.2%
Projects	9.3%

Table 4 - Results of mapping & scouting activity

The interactive map is available on the PROCEDIN website¹. It collects the totality of the stakeholders found in the scouting and mapping activity. This map is set to facilitate the research of POI stakeholders across Europe through a visual and geographical assessment. With this tool, the users will be able to assess the number of stakeholders present in a specific geographical area of their interest, they will be able to filter them based on the stakeholder category, and learn about their main services through a brief description that is provided. Each entity is linked to its respective website as well. The interactive map will be continuously updated by F6S, even after the end of the PROCEDIN project, since the project website's domain will be available for 5 years. This decision was taken to ensure a higher engagement, traffic, and use of the resources provided by the PROCEDIN project, serving as a landmark for POI stakeholders. Both project partners and the website users will be able to provide new resources suggestions through the dedicated section on the website.

¹ <https://procedin.eu/stakeholder-map/>

Figure 6 – Examples of results from the interactive map of POI stakeholders with contact details concealed for confidentiality

5 Reporting on clusters' needs, capabilities and barriers to POI

5.1 Methodology

To deliver the “POI learner archetype”, only the Innovation Demand and Innovation Supply clusters were considered, since they include groups of POI professionals that are directly interested in learning and therefore implementing Procurement of Innovation. Multipliers and Projects clusters refer to categories which support or maximise the effort of the first-mentioned clusters. Therefore, the resources identified to learn and analyse the barriers and needs on POI training and implementation were directly taken from the Innovation Demand and Innovation Supply stakeholders.

The resources used include both internal information collected through PROCEDIN activities, and externally sourced knowledge from academic papers, cited in the results below, and partners' prior project experience. The resources produced directly by the PROCEDIN project activities are: (i) *T1.1 and T1.2 and T1.3 surveys on resources for Buyers, SMEs and High Tech Start-Ups(HTSUS)*; (ii) *T2.3 Interviews to identify procurement leaders' key barriers and enablers for embedding POI (early results)*; (iii) *D2.1 Database on POI stakeholders mapping*.

The aggregated analysis was facilitated by UT partners providing insights from academic research that served as a wider context for the evidence from within the PROCEDIN project. Indeed, the needs and barriers mentioned by the interviewees or survey participants were consistent with those found in the literature, even though the interviews provided more precise and real-time information and therefore a direct validation of the present results.

The interviewees (T2.3) and survey respondents (WP1) represent a large pool of stakeholders, including entities with more and with less POI experience. Specifically, the (i) *T1.1 and T1.2 and T1.3 surveys on resources for Buyers, SMEs and HTSUS* provided 72 responses from Innovation Demand stakeholders and 15 from the Innovation Supply side, coming from a total of 22 EU and non-EU countries across Europe. The Innovation Demand respondents include policymakers, legal advisors, and technical advisors from local municipalities or universities while Innovation Supply respondents include service or product suppliers from SMEs or Universities. Several interviews belonging to *T2.3 Interviews to identify procurement leaders' key barriers and enablers for embedding POI* were used (interviews are ongoing). Two of these concern a highly experienced POI procurer, one has little experience in its country and the remaining one has average experience. (iii) *D2.1 Database on POI stakeholders mapping* provided insights on geographical location, company size and focus activity, from 82 entities within the Innovation Supply Stakeholder group and 55 from the Innovation Demand cluster. Further information on the Innovation Supply needs and barriers was provided by the practical knowledge gained by the Tenderio platform, a service specialised in improving SMEs' access to public procurement, of which PEDAL Consulting is the owner.

The mentioned gaps, needs, and barriers should be considered when developing strategies to support the Innovation Supply and Demand entities in their learning and innovation processes. Tailored programs and initiatives can help address these challenges and facilitate their development and contributions to the broader innovation ecosystem.

How to read the results

In sections 5.2 and 5.3 all the mentioned resources were analysed and aggregated to understand the main needs and barriers of the stakeholder. They provide a deep explanation of the identified topics,

providing examples, background context and citations. In sections 5.2.1 and 5.3.1 the reader can find the archetypes of the two analysed clusters. In these, a list of the main characteristics, needs and barriers was summarised from the wider pool of information provided from the previous sections.

5.2 Innovation Demand needs, capabilities and barriers to POI

As described in paragraph (i) of section 2.1, the Innovation Demand cluster includes organisations or individuals, from the public or private domain, who express a requirement or desire for novel products, services, or solutions with the scope of enhancing social, economic or environmental conditions through the procurement and implementation of innovative solutions. They include procurement organisations at municipality, regional or national level.

Private purchasing bodies were not considered for this report.

Needs and capabilities

They encounter several needs which can be classified into six main categories:

1. Skill Development and unpacking competences

Learning needs includes hard skills (e.g. writing requirements, supplier scouting), and soft skills which are those skills needed to cope with complexity and uncertainty in projects, collaboration across organisational and functional boundaries and creative/entrepreneurial mindset. Developing these is more challenging – there is a significant element of cultural change and attitudinal shifts.

Standardized skills models are required to educate and train individuals. However, it's crucial to account for cultural differences in Procurement and Supply Management (PSM) competencies (Stek et al., 2022). These models encompass technical skills, strategic purchasing approaches, and behavioural skills (Tassabehji and Moorhouse, 2008).

Procurement professionals must acquire new strategic skills to effectively manage global supply chains and enhance organisational success (Amann and Essig, 2015). This entails fostering creativity, inventiveness, and holistic thinking, which are vital for innovative procurement (Stek et al., 2022), activities that can help to enhance the adoption of circular economy solutions.

Key competencies sought after in POI professionals include negotiation, communication, salesmanship and relationship management with a focus on collaborative competencies (Feiser et al., 2011).

Salesmanship skills are necessary for purchasers to effectively "sell" innovative ideas within their organisations (Stek et al., 2022). This is crucial also to highlight the contribution of internal workers leaner and more willing to foster POI inside of their organisation.

(Bals et al. 2019) made a key contribution to the Purchasing and Supply Management competencies and clusters identified by Tassabehji and Moorhouse (2008). They highlight that the most crucial new competency area is related to digitalisation (e.g. 'Automation'), innovation (e.g. 'Innovative sourcing') and 'Sustainability'. They also identified 11 new competencies to the interpersonal skills cluster, most of them in the intersection between competencies and traits (e.g. 'Passion')." All the competencies are listed in the table below.

Current Competencies	Future Competencies
Analytical skills	Analytical Skills
Basic knowledge on PSM role & processes	Automation
Communication skills	Big Data Analytics
Cross-functional abilities & knowledge	Computer Literacy
Interpersonal Communication	eProcurement Technology
Negotiation	Holistic supply chain thinking
Stakeholder Relationship Management	Process optimisation
Strategic sourcing	Strategic Sourcing
Strategic thinking	Strategic thinking
Sustainability	Sustainability

Figure 7 - Top ten current and future competencies for PSM

In POI, it's important to focus on cost management to meet delivery goals. People specializing in delivery often lack contract management skills, which become more critical for broader objectives. For those focused on delivery, training to reduce costs and improve forecasting can be beneficial. However, investing in contract law classes, legal knowledge and commercial skills training may not be the most efficient use of resources, as the primary focus is on delivery goals, not complex contract management. (Stek & Schiele, 2021) Training focuses on technical skills, while development concentrates on enhancing interpersonal abilities and overall company or group performance. Relying solely on training in POI is insufficient for adapting to the ever-changing landscape and achieving process efficiency; development is equally essential. This entails all aspects of HR management, including implementing effective recruitment practices, conducting performance appraisals, crafting personal development plans, and providing coaching and mentoring. These activities have a direct influence on the performance of a public buyer .

Certain learning requirements pertain exclusively to the public sector and its various subcategories, while others have applicability across different sectors. It is essential to distinguish between what can be applied universally and what is tailored to a specific sector. A significant portion of the issues encountered by public procurement professionals revolves around enhancing their strategic procurement capabilities in a broader context, such as effectively collaborating within multifunctional teams. Likewise, teams that have cultivated expertise in green procurement have acquired valuable knowledge that can be utilized in other areas, including POI.

According to Stek et al. (2022), adopting and embedding POI requires developments in competencies which also align with wider changes in the public management/administration and industry 5.0, encompassing more attention to culture and soft skills.

There is a need to align the political will/support for a strategic approach to procurement and the capabilities of the procurement professional like it’s described in this study by Tassabehji and Moorhouse (2008).

Fig. 2. Procurement effectiveness matrix.

Figure 8- Procurement effectiveness matrix. (Sourc: Tassabehji and Moorhouse, 2008).

Human resource development (HRD) is essential for organisations to establish a long-term strategy, ensuring the presence of necessary skills at the appropriate levels within the procurement hierarchy (Amann and Essig, 2015).

Collaboration and cooperation among innovation stakeholders can lead to higher efficiency in innovative initiatives, particularly when smaller or less experienced stakeholders are involved and when a procurer body has a dedicated team for POI, which doesn’t occur often in small municipalities or areas where innovation procurement culture is not well established.

2. Cross-Functional Collaboration

Procurement professionals should engage in cross-functional collaboration, recognizing that cultural backgrounds can influence perceptions of trust, commitment, and dependence in supplier relationships (Amann and Essig, 2015). This collaboration should extend to both internal and external interfaces to develop value-adding supply strategies.

Collaborative competencies are essential for working jointly with other organisations to produce public value effectively. Identifying critical skills and competencies is crucial for achieving current and future programmatic results (Getha-Taylor, 2008).

Cooperation among stakeholders is vital for the reuse of products, components, and recycling of materials, particularly in the context of Circular Economy (CE) transitions. Monitoring CE progress in product chains provides insights into the development of new relationships and the role of innovation in technology, product design, and revenue models (Potting et al., 2017).

Building strong relationships with suppliers is crucial for sourcing and implementing innovation, but also cooperation between smaller and bigger procurer entities can enrich their knowledge and resource capacity.

Initiatives like URBACT local groups and international projects have been valuable for exchanging knowledge and ideas among various departments and stakeholders.

3. Sector-Specific Understanding

Policymakers and practitioners need a deeper understanding of the specific requirements of SME suppliers in different sectors to enhance their participation and success in the public procurement process (Loader and Norton, 2015).

4. Socio-Institutional Change

Facilitating the adoption of innovative solutions requires reviewing both written and unwritten rules, customs, and beliefs. This socio-institutional change is crucial.

Support for innovation is essential, especially for the successful implementation of radical technological innovations. This includes building a new Technological Innovation System (Potting et al., 2017).

5. Specific Training and Resources

Innovation Demand stakeholders require specific training and access to high-quality case studies with detailed information and clear legislative requirements. This includes guidance on ensuring the innovative character of procurement practices. These resources are essential to provide guidelines and proof of the validity of POI tools in terms of resources invested and tangible results.

Training should cover various and specific topics, including addressing challenges such as increasing energy costs, supply chain shortages, human rights, fair trade, supplier risk assessment and evaluation, aligning sustainability criteria with budget constraints, implementing long-term views on product lifetime cycle cost. Other topics include legal assistance, ready-made order forms through the "Dynamic Purchasing System," energy efficiency contracts and specifications, measures for decarbonization, circular procurement, sustainability practices, handling complex technical issues, quality assessment, inflation clauses and solutions, concrete sustainability solutions, contract management, social responsibility and audits, digital applications into public procurement processes.

Even though there are a lot of resources available, they are often not easy to find. This highlights a potential need for improved accessibility to innovative resources for procurement professionals.

6. Simplification of the POI Process

Many initiatives to increase adoption of POI are centred on developing knowledge of EU public procurement instruments for larger (higher value and complexity projects) projects and encouraging their uptake. This presents a steep and resource-intensive learning curve. An important theme from T2.3 interviewees is that encouraging more innovation on procurement and contracting can also be about simplifying processes. They noted that this could be by including innovation-related criteria (as has been done with green and social aspects) in traditional contracts. This significantly lowers the threshold for knowledge and resources needed for implementing innovation.

Criteria for various markets, circular economy, and reuse should be updated and integrated. Long-term contracts should be developed and implemented to guarantee the achievement of specific goals, especially in areas like food and catering, energy, and services with reduced harmful impacts. This activity will also enhance the long-term relationship between public buyers and suppliers. Adaptations should also be made to accommodate small public administrations.

The findings demonstrate that there are indeed significant obstacles to implementing Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI), and these obstacles are prevalent across European Union member

states. Time-consuming processes and complexity are major challenges when it comes to effectively implementing innovation procurement in the public sector.

Barriers

Innovation Demand stakeholders are associated with six main barriers to POI learning and implementation:

1. Resistance to Change

Internal stakeholders may resist the integration of new procurement strategies and structures, creating hurdles in innovation implementation (Amann and Essig, 2015). This resistance is often linked to fears related to resource, time constraints, budget concerns, availability in the supply chain, and the perception of higher costs associated with innovation compared to traditional solutions. Furthermore, low awareness of the benefits of procurement of innovation (POI) is attributed to the scarcity of case studies.

Traditional hiring methods, such as exams and IQ tests, are still favored by some decision-makers, despite the proven effectiveness of competency-based approaches (Getha-Taylor, 2008). The former are useful for assessing knowledge (eg of contract law). The latter are needed to assess, for example, a potential recruit's disposition and skills for working collaboratively.

Socio-institutional lock-in, driven by existing ways of consumption, production, and business practices, results in inertia that complicates Circular Economy (CE) transitions (Potting et al., 2017).

Procurement of innovation should be embedded as a routine or commonplace practice rather than being limited to high-profile initiatives. This suggests a barrier in integrating innovation into everyday procurement processes and that that change management and communication strategies are crucial to overcome resistance and facilitate innovation procurement.

There are entrenched work methodologies, particularly among influential, experienced technical professionals, which may not align with the functional aspects needed for innovation projects. This is due to the practical and technical experience of their roles which often is not used in collaborative settings as the ones present in project development and implementation. Good communication, coordination and awareness of POI practices are needed to collaborate effectively.

2. Directionality/Criteria Failure

The current economy prioritizes cost reduction and functionality improvement, neglecting the efficient consumption of resources and materials, thus resulting in inefficient selection criteria applied to POI (Potting et al., 2017). The lack of clear criteria is also linked to the complexity of POI tools, which often don't state clear innovation goals, leading to a risk of inefficient innovative solutions and resources wasted. Encouraging change means changing the working context and incentive structures.

3. Lack of Qualified Professionals

Organisations may struggle to find and retain personnel capable of effectively developing and managing POI since it requires specific skilled professionals. In some cases, funding is not sufficient to provide fair and attractive salaries to these experts who therefore lack motivation to take such a high risk activity, and the additional burden that occurs especially in the earlier stages of the POI learning journey.

Validation studies to establish the competency link to performance are often skipped due to the high associated costs (Getha-Taylor, 2008).

The existing literature on procurement skills lacks differentiation between types of purchasers and their distinct objectives (those working on routine purchases, versus more innovation oriented contracts), leading to a lack of clarity on the necessary skills. Time constraints also hinder the selection and prioritization of learning objectives (Stek et al., 2022).

Lack of qualified professionals is particularly evident in decentralized procurement settings, coupled with a lack of training and familiarity with POI, leading to fragmented knowledge and resources and a lack of momentum in the learning journey. Contracting authorities are often expected to be experts in their targeted field (e.g. energy, construction, technology etc.), which is not always the case. Alternatively, coordinating activities with technical experts should be addressed and implemented.

4. Complexity and risk aversion

Various complexities, including legal and regulatory constraints, risk aversion, lack of information, and organisational culture, pose significant barriers (De et al., 2020).

Government purchasing laws and difficulties in proving and evaluating innovation, as well as a lack of predetermined evaluation criteria or established mechanisms, result in lengthy procedures, low participant interest, administrative burdens, and the procurement of low-quality products. Embedding clearer criteria to public contracts could simplify the evaluation and proposal activity.

The evidence regarding *risk aversion* as key barrier to implementing POI is inconsistent. Statistical analysis provided in the academic papers does not provide strong evidence to categorize risk as a significant barrier to PPI, and yet this was stated in the collected interviews and answers to the WP1 surveys. Therefore, risk aversion needs further consideration. It is perhaps too broad a 'catch-all' term which needs careful exploration, for example distinguishing between change resistant ways of working in organisations (eg where legal compliance dominates procurement thinking, rather than being impact and outcomes focused) and an individual employee's reluctance to start the POI learning journey where they already feel overwhelmed by the volume of 'regular' contracts they work on. The engaged stakeholders indeed often aren't sure about the potential positive implementation results, since there are few detailed case studies available and therefore lack of evidence that POI tools are timely and costly efficient.

5. Cultural Differences

Procurement professionals may face challenges in implementing innovation procurement due to cultural backgrounds characterized by low trust in government, bureaucratic complexity, and prioritization of standard procurement practices. In some countries, the procurement culture is risk-averse when it comes to new, unexplored innovation methods.

Internal political struggles and a lack of power within organisations can hinder procurement professionals from effectively implementing and managing strategies (Tassabehji and Moorhouse, 2008).

Ignoring cultural differences can lead to inaccuracies and impractical outcomes, as a universal procurement approach does not exist. Country-specific cultural factors influence POI implementation (Stek et al., 2022).

6. Unmatched Communication and Cooperation

There is a lack of awareness and knowledge regarding POI and the market, along with a disconnect between the market and buyers.

Communication gaps exist in the startup world, and there are difficulties in establishing long-term relationships with innovative suppliers due to the necessity for re-tendering after a few years, as well as complexities and uncertainties.

The most critical activity for experienced public procurers was the engagement of citizens since it is increasingly becoming more essential to provide a shared and efficient solution, but it requires specific training and methods.

Innovation Demand POI learner archetype

In this report, our primary focus is on the POI Innovation Demand cluster, representing distinct stakeholder groups. These stakeholders include a diverse range of organisations and individuals, spanning both public and private sectors, all driven by a common goal: the procurement and implementation of innovative solutions to elevate social, economic, and environmental conditions. They are situated at different administrative levels (municipal, regional, national, with the PROCEDIN focus being on municipal level). Particularly, it is common to find less resources (financially and professionally) in smaller procuring entities. Barriers to POI are greater where there is less innovation culture, due to major financial burdens of a country or where there is less trust in the public administrations.

However, there are alternative approaches to consider. For instance, organisations or teams seeking to embrace or incorporate Procurement of Innovation (POI) could be categorized based on the development pathways they are navigating. To achieve this, we can differentiate between their initial starting point and their objectives:

High Resources - Low Intentions to High Resources - High Intentions: this distinction accounts for entities with a strong team of purchasing professionals and robust systems. Their intentions may encompass a desire to adopt innovation partnerships, engage in market consultations, primarily within the context of larger innovation projects. Alternatively, they may be looking to introduce innovation criteria into traditional contracting, following a more subtle and low-key approach.

Additionally, it's worth considering the extent and focus of political support. For example, in the case of green mobility, councillors may exhibit varying degrees of interest, potentially emphasizing either green initiatives or mobility-related aspects.

Note that private purchasing entities are not encompassed within the scope of this report.

The main needs and barriers are therefore summarised as follows:

Skill development and competences

In POI, especially in Circular Economy (CE) and Green Mobility procurement, stakeholders require a diverse skill set encompassing both hard and soft skills. This includes technical competencies such as composing innovative requirements and scouting suppliers, along with soft skills necessary for handling complexity, fostering collaboration, and creative thinking. Standardized skills models are essential but must accommodate cultural nuances.

Key competencies identified are: negotiation, communication, relationship management, multifunctional collaboration, salesmanship, digitalisation, innovative sourcing, sustainability, holistic supply chain thinking, contract and costs management.

Addressing resistance to change and legal complexities requires skill development in these areas. Procurers don't need only to have training focused on technical skills, but also development, meaning: implementing effective recruitment practices, conducting performance appraisals, crafting personal development plans, and providing coaching and mentoring. As it can be assessed, adopting, and embedding POI requires developments in competences which also align with wider changes in the public management/administration and industry 5.0², encompassing more attention to culture and soft skills.

Contracting authorities are often expected to be experts in their targeted field (e.g. energy, construction, technology etc.), which is not always the case; municipalities contract across a vast range of categories and may lack category specific knowledge needed for innovation. Alternatively, coordinating activities with technical experts should be addressed and implemented.

Lack of qualified professionals is particularly evident in decentralized procurement settings, coupled with a lack of training and familiarity with POI. In some cases, funding is not sufficient to provide fair salaries to these experts who therefore lack motivation to take such a high risk activity. Special attention should be therefore given when designing the financial resources for a POI initiative, since a skilled and motivated workforce is the base for its success.

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Breque, M., De Nul, L., Petridis, A., Industry 5.0 – Towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/308407>

Specific training and resources

Training programs should cover diverse topics, including sustainability, legal aspects, and complex technical challenges. Accessing these resources efficiently is essential. Additionally, validation studies linking competency development to performance improvement are crucial. The availability of these resources can significantly impact the success of procurement initiatives in these domains.

Specifically, the training needs identified by the engaged Innovation Demand stakeholders are: increasing energy costs, supply chain shortages, human rights, fair trade, supplier risk assessment and evaluation, aligning sustainability criteria with budget constraints, implementing long-term views on product lifetime cycle cost, legal assistance, ready-made order forms through the "Dynamic Purchasing System," energy efficiency contracts and specifications, measures for decarbonization, circular procurement, sustainability practices, handling complex technical issues, quality assessment, inflation clauses and solutions, concrete sustainability solutions, contract management, social responsibility and audits, digital applications into public procurement processes.

The most requested topics focused on: inflation clauses and solutions, solutions to increasing energy costs, aligning sustainability criteria with budget constraints, contract management.

It's important to note that, following the opinion of the survey respondents, the most efficient way to learn and understand POI is through detailed case studies.

Cross-functional collaboration

Effective CE and Green Mobility procurement hinges on cross-functional collaboration, involving both internal and external interfaces. Cultural backgrounds can impact trust, commitment, and communication within supplier relationships. Overcoming cultural disparities and establishing efficient communication, coordination, and awareness are key to successful collaboration. This extends to coordinating activities with technical experts and experiences procurers, enhancing the overall procurement process. Cooperation is essential at crossed level, meaning both between suppliers and procurers but also within these two categories, from those with more resources and capacity to those with less. Initiatives like URBACT local groups and international projects have been valuable for exchanging knowledge and ideas among various departments and stakeholders.

Sector-specific understanding

Understanding sector-specific requirements is vital, especially in interactions with Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME) suppliers. Procurement professionals must tailor their approaches to accommodate the unique demands and constraints of different sectors, enhancing SME participation and success in CE and Green Mobility procurement.

Socio-institutional change and cultural difference

Stakeholders may resist the integration of new procurement strategies and structures. This resistance is often linked to fears related to recourse, time constraints, budget concerns, availability in the supply chain, traditional existing ways of consumption, and the perception of higher costs associated with innovation compared to traditional solutions. Also cultural backgrounds significantly influence procurement practices. Furthermore, low awareness of the benefits of Procurement of Innovation (POI) is attributed to the scarcity of case studies.

Successful CE and Green Mobility procurement necessitates not only technical competencies but also socio-institutional change. This involves revising established rules, customs, and beliefs to align with transformative goals. Political support and institutional changes are essential for innovation adoption. Recognizing and addressing also cultural disparities is essential for tailoring strategies to align with specific cultural factors, ensuring the success of POI efforts.

Simplification of the POI process

Procurement Of Innovation is generally perceived as a complex tool. This originates from the fact that it is a relatively new tool, therefore not much experience and case studies are available, but also because the definition of “innovation” and the requirements/criteria are often not clear or they don't have established mechanisms. Time-consuming processes and complexity are major challenges when it comes to effectively implementing innovation procurement in the public sector. Long-term contracts should be developed and implemented to guarantee the achievement of specific goals, this activity will enhance also a long-term relationship between public buyers and suppliers.

The engaged stakeholders suggested to integrate innovation-related selection criteria into traditional contracts to incentivize innovation adoption.

Unmatched communication and cooperation

Bridging communication gaps, fostering cooperation among stakeholders, including startups and citizens, and engaging in efficient citizen involvement are crucial aspects of innovation procurement in these domains. Critical activities are especially communication gaps in with the start-up world, difficulties in establishing long-term relationships with innovative suppliers, the engagement of citizens and the right methods to do this activity efficiently.

Concluding, Innovation Demand stakeholders face similar obstacles and requirements for learning and implementing POI. Even though procurers might differ in size, political and cultural background, we can identify the common perception of POI as a complex and time-consuming tool with a lack of standardised procedure for innovation assessment. The common challenges include lack of proper training and skills assessment, especially in collaborative skills and development strategies. In places where POI benefits are not perceived, besides the internal hurdles of a country/municipality, we can link this to a lack of awareness-raising initiatives and prepared workforce. The most requested solution to this issue was providing case studies from which learning the best practices and POI implementation from a practical and efficient point of view. This highlights the need of cooperation between smaller and bigger entities, as well as between procurers and suppliers.

5.3 Innovation Supply needs, capabilities, and barriers to POI

As described in paragraph (ii) of section 2.1, the Innovation Supply cluster includes entities like SMEs, startups, spin-offs, universities, incubators, and technology centers. They represent the essential components of the innovation ecosystem since their activity is focused on creating and providing innovative products, services or solutions. Innovation Supply players are considered learners in the procurement of innovation process. They continuously adapt and innovate, making valuable contributions to the innovation ecosystem. Their capacity-building process involves addressing

knowledge gaps, resource limitations, and market challenges. Their involvement often spans research, development, and the commercialization of fresh technologies or concepts. Procurement of Innovation is relatively a new tool that needs a strong training and awareness-raising efforts for suppliers involved in the procurement of innovation. These are crucial to facilitate a smooth and mutually beneficial collaboration between suppliers and the procuring organisation.

Some potential gaps to be overcome in the POI process by Innovation Suppliers include gaps in knowledge of procurement procedures and legal regulations. Resource gaps can hinder their chances to access to financial resources and therefore skilled talent or infrastructure. Market awareness gaps on the other hand can lead to potential mismatches between the innovation and the real market needs. In this aggregated report, a special focus was directed to entities working in with green mobility and circular economy, to contextualise their needs and barriers based on the specific characteristics of these fields of activity.

Needs and capabilities

Key elements to be considered in the education and training of suppliers are the following. Their needs be classified into 7 main categories:

1. Understanding procurement procedures, regulations, and resources

Suppliers need to be well informed about relevant procurement procedures, legal frameworks, documentation requirements, and compliance standards specific to their industry. They should also be aware of available sources, such as research and development funding, grants, or innovation support programs, to enhance their offerings.

The first stage, involving the preparation and submission of tenders, has proven to be particularly problematic, primarily due to concerns related to the specification.

Nevertheless, in various other aspects, the surveyed companies have shared opinions and experiences that align with the broader SME population. This includes issues such as collaborative tender submissions, decisions primarily driven by cost, and inadequate feedback from public buyers. In summary, public buyers often prioritize cost in their decisions and provide insufficient feedback, which is a common challenge faced by SMEs.

Many circular economy entities would benefit from specialized training and education programs focused on circular economy principles, sustainable materials management, and waste reduction strategies.

2. Innovation assessment

Suppliers need to understand how their innovative solutions will be evaluated, considering criteria such as technical feasibility, scalability, cost-effectiveness, and potential impact. They need to be aware of ethical and sustainability requirements or standards, such as environmental impact assessments and social responsibility guidelines. Through these tools, they should be able to align with the procuring organisation's sustainability goals.

3. Intellectual Property (IP) rights and data privacy

Clear agreements on IP ownership and usage should be made transparent to suppliers, covering aspects like patents, copyrights, and trade secrets. If sensitive data is involved, suppliers must be educated on data security and privacy best practices to protect confidential information.

4. Risk management, project management and reporting

Innovation Supply stakeholders should be aware of potential risks associated with developing and delivering innovative solutions, including project delays, technical issues, and regulatory compliance challenges. They should be well-informed about project management expectations, including reporting, communication, and progress tracking.

5. Contractual and legal obligations and quality assurance

Educating suppliers on procurement contract terms and conditions, payment terms, deliverables, milestones, and dispute resolution mechanism is crucial. Suppliers need to comprehend the quality assurance and testing requirements, aligning their solutions with the procuring organisation's quality standards.

6. Collaboration and communication including continuous feedback

Building collaborations with other stakeholders, such as research institutions, larger corporations, and government agencies, can help innovation supply entities access additional resources and expertise. It is also important to emphasise the importance of open and effective communication between suppliers and the procuring organisation, addressing concerns promptly and regularly updating. Suppliers should be encouraged to see feedback from the procuring organisation and use it for continuous improvement of their product or services, improving coordination and cooperation skills. Collaboration is crucial not only between innovation demand and supply clusters, but also between smaller and bigger suppliers. Micro (<10 employees) and small (<50 employees) entities have indeed generally less access to resources and dedicated compliance teams to face regulatory challenges or time for dedicated training and education. Medium-sized (<250 employees) suppliers usually have more specialised workforce, but this doesn't avoid having need of support and cooperation to solve market entry, regulatory and financial resources barriers.

Initiatives like URBACT local groups and international projects have been valuable for exchanging knowledge and ideas among various departments and stakeholders.

7. Market entry and scaling

Startups and smaller suppliers may benefit from education on market entry and scaling, market research and validation, including support in conducting market research, understanding consumer preferences, validating the innovations in the market, access to mentoring and business development support.

Barriers

Innovation Supply stakeholders identified 5 main barriers to POI learning and implementation:

1. Financial barriers

Limited access to funding can impede the development and commercialisation of innovative solutions. This is particularly critical for green mobility and circular economy projects, which often require substantial initial investment. Incubators and accelerators require financial resources to support startups' growth, invest in innovative projects, and provide access to funding opportunities.

Start-ups, particularly suffer of resource limitations, including access to funding, research facilities, and experienced personnel.

2. Regulatory and compliance barriers

Complex regulatory requirements can be challenging to navigate, especially for startups and smaller entities and for specific requirements associated with green mobility including emissions standards and safety regulations or for the dynamic circular economy sector and its regulations on circular materials, waste management, recycling and life-cycle analysis policies.

3. Resource constraints

Suppliers may face resource constraints, including access to state-of-the-art technology, skilled workforce, or research facilities. This applies specifically to micro sized (<10 employees) entities.

Specific to green mobility, some entities may have technical knowledge gaps in areas related to green mobility technologies, such as electric propulsion systems, alternative fuels, or sustainable transportation solutions. In some cases, the lack of adequate infrastructure, such as charging stations for electric vehicles, can pose barriers to the adoption of green mobility solutions.

The complex supply chains on which green mobility depends, such for components like batteries, can introduce vulnerabilities and delays. Same applies for circular economy entities, which need to work closely with supply chain partners to integrate sustainable materials and processes into existing systems.

4. Market entry barriers

Breaking into competitive markets can be difficult, requiring strategies to differentiate and gain market share. If the entity's innovation focus is not clearly defined, it may face challenges in entering the market and differentiating itself from competitors or similar organisations.

Some innovations, like those related to circular economy, may face barriers to market adoption due to existing practices and buyer preferences. These innovations can be complex and require a comprehensive approach. The green mobility market is highly competitive, making it challenging for smaller entities to gain market share and establish themselves as significant players.

Shifting buyer behavior towards green mobility or circular economy options can also be a slow process, and entities may face resistance to adopting new technologies due to the cheaper and more established network of traditional means of transportation or standard products, even though this represents higher aggregated costs in the long run.

For incubators, helping startups break into competitive markets involving the public sector and gain market share is a main challenge, since they need to address also regulatory compliances and technological risks.

5. Risk aversion and resistance to social-institutional changes

Developing and implementing new green technologies can involve technical risks and uncertainties. There might be fear of failure which can inhibit experimentation and innovation. Suppliers may be small and agile, but they need to understand and navigate barriers and enablers affecting often larger buyer organisations, and other parties (eg in a consortium of suppliers).

CE transitions aiming for increased circularity necessitate a greater degree of socio-institutional modifications across the product chain, making their oversight challenging.

Innovation Supply POI learner archetype

This cluster encompasses a variety of entities, such as SMEs, startups, spin-offs, universities, incubators, and technology centres. These entities play a crucial role in the innovation ecosystem, concentrating their efforts on creating and offering innovative products, services, or solutions.

Their journey involves addressing gaps in knowledge of procurement procedures, legal regulations, resource limitations, and market challenges. Their involvement spans activities from research and development to the commercialization of new technologies and concepts. Given that Procurement of Innovation is a relatively new tool, these suppliers require robust training and awareness-building initiatives. Such efforts are essential to enable effective and mutually beneficial collaborations between suppliers and the procuring organisations.

The main needs and barriers are therefore summarised as follows:

Comprehending procurement procedures and regulations

Complex regulatory requirements can be challenging to navigate, especially for startups and smaller entities, especially when dealing with green mobility or CE standards and regulations. Suppliers must gain a comprehensive understanding of relevant procurement procedures, legal frameworks, documentation requirements, and industry-specific compliance standards. Additionally, they should be informed about available resources, such as research and development funding, grants, or innovation support programs.

The third stage, involving the preparation and submission of tenders, has proven to be particularly problematic, primarily due to concerns related to the specification. Indeed, to succeed in procurement of innovation, suppliers must comprehend how their innovative solutions will be evaluated. This includes considering criteria such as technical feasibility, scalability, cost-effectiveness, and potential impact. The lack of clear innovation assessment criteria can lead to inefficient solutions and wasted resources.

The main issues identified by SME population are: collaborative tender submissions, decisions primarily driven by cost, and inadequate feedback from public buyers.

Addressing resource gaps

Resource constraints, including limited access to funding, access to state-of-the-art technology, research facilities, and a skilled workforce, can impede the development and commercialization of innovative solutions. These constraints are particularly prominent among smaller entities within this

cluster. Specifically, limited access to funding is critical for green mobility and circular economy projects, which often require substantial initial investment. Start-ups, particularly suffer of resource limitations.

Navigating market awareness gaps

Suppliers need a deep understanding of the market landscape and its evolving needs. Without this awareness, there's a risk of developing innovations that do not align with market demands, potentially resulting in disconnects between innovation and market needs.

Intellectual Property (IP) Rights and data privacy

Transparency regarding IP ownership and data security practices is crucial for suppliers. Clear agreements on patents, copyrights, and trade secrets protect sensitive information. Without such clarity, disputes can arise, compromising confidential information.

Risk Management, Project Management, legal obligations

Innovation supply stakeholders should understand project and contract management procedures. They need to understand and be familiar with risk management, project reporting, and compliance awareness to mitigate challenges like projects delays, technical issues, and regulatory hurdles. It is crucial also to understand payment terms, deliverables, milestones, and quality standards to avoid disputes and subpar deliverables.

Collaboration and communication, including continuous feedback

Effective communication, prompt issue resolution, and regular feedback are essential for successful partnerships. Suppliers should use feedback to continuously improve their products or services. Collaboration is crucial not only between innovation demand and supply clusters, but also between smaller and bigger suppliers.

Procurement of Innovation perception should be shifted to a more sustainable and everyday approach. For this, change management and communication strategies are crucial to overcome resistance and facilitate innovation procurement. It is essential to encourage more people working within organisations to have a forward-looking approach and seek cooperation, even though it may not always involve troubleshooting or crisis management.

Market entry and scaling

Startups and smaller suppliers may require support in market research, validation, and business development. Understanding consumer preferences, validating innovations in the market, and gaining access to mentoring and business development support are essential for gaining a foothold in competitive markets. Market entry challenges and resistance to new technologies can hinder startups' growth and market share.

In essence, Innovation Supply stakeholders face similar obstacles and requirements during their innovation journeys. These common challenges encompass limitations in resources, gaps in market awareness, the imperative for funding access, mentorship, and guidance, as well as difficulties linked to market competition, technological risks, and compliance with regulations. To achieve successful innovation and growth, it is vital for these entities to address these shared challenges through collaboration, mentorship, and efficient resource management and availability.

Although the specific challenges and available resources may differ based on the entity type, these recurrent patterns underscore the universal need to address resource constraints, secure funding, and navigate regulatory landscapes for successful innovation within the "Innovation Supply" stakeholder group, encompassing Incubator/Accelerator and Start-up/Spin-off entities. Collaboration and mentorship also emerge as crucial elements in conquering these shared challenges.

PROCEDIN project's activities align with the needs identified in this report.

6 Next steps

The compilation of relevant stakeholders and the identification of their needs and barriers in participating in and embedding POI, marks a fundamental step in advancing WP3 and WP5, and complements the forthcoming results of T2.3 interviews on leadership and embedding POI. Specifically, WP3 will focus on legal frameworks and the delivery of legal assistance training, including also support arrangements for tools and best practices. WP5 is focused on dissemination and communication activities. More precisely, the gathered stakeholder contacts will be employed to initiate communication and assess their degree of interest, commitment, and preparedness to engage in more comprehensive processes, producing tailored knowledge on POI. The level of their engagement in the project's endeavors will also hinge on the particular form of support required. The database will continue to accept new stakeholder contacts that may prove beneficial for the objectives of the task. The engagement of universities will take place in WP4, broadening the community involved in the enhancement of POI while consulting with these entities to teach and inspire future innovation procurement leaders.

PROCEDIN GANTT		Oct-21	Nov-21	Dec-21	Jan-22	Feb-22	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	
Leader		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	
WP1 Resource Mapping																										
T1.1 Survey POI resources for buyers	Haarlem																									
T1.2 Survey POI resources from buyers for SMEs and start-ups	F&S																									
T1.3 Survey of resources for SMEs and start-ups from other sources	F&S																									
WP2 Engagement and Recruitment of Stakeholders																										
T2.1 Mapping and clustering stakeholders	Pedal																									
T2.2 Calls for expressions of interest	F&S																									
T2.3 Identify procurement leaders' key barriers and enablers for embedding POI	UT																									
WP3 Legal Framework																										
T3.1 Develop legal framework materials	Gabrovo																									
T3.2 Provide legal assistance	Gabrovo																									
T3.3 Deliver legal assistance trainings	Gabrovo																									
T3.4 Set up support arrangements for tools and best practices	Haarlem																									
WP4 Future leaders																										
T4.1 Survey European universities	UT																									
T4.2 Promote city stakeholders-university engagement	Gabrovo																									
T4.3 Select and customise resources	UT																									
WP5 Dissemination																										
T5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities	F&S																									
T5.2 Ecosystem building and impact report	Haarlem																									
T5.3 Exploitation, replicability and sustainability	Haarlem																									
WP6 Project Management																										
T6.1 Coordination and quality management	UT																									
T6.2 Data management	Pedal																									
T6.3 Project meetings and reporting	Pedal																									

Figure 9 – PROCEDIN project Gantt chart

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Annex I: Sample extracts from the stakeholders mapping and scouting database

With organisation names removed (for confidentiality)

1. Innovation Demand

Innovation Demand stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	NUTS 2021 classification	Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation (if available)	Short description* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in PROCEDIN)
Central Purchasing body	National			The office is an independent central body of the state administration, headed by the chairman of the office.
Central Purchasing body	National			In the field of public procurement, it represents the Slovak Republic externally. works in expert working is the national innovation agency in
Central Purchasing body	National			Germany and is involved in innovation procurement through programs
Central Purchasing body	National			With its Programme for Innovation Procurement (PIP), the Government of Flanders aims to use its substantial purchasing power strategically as a catalyst for innovation.
Central Purchasing body	National			Finnish Funding Agency for Technology and Innovation, a part of Finnish Ministry of Employment and the Economy, is the most important public funding agency for research funding in Finland.
Central Purchasing body	International			government agency which is part of the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy. helps entrepreneurs and organisations to invest, develop and expand their businesses and projects. Both in the Netherlands and abroad.
Central Purchasing body				Vinnova is Sweden’s innovation agency and try to help to build Sweden's innovation capacity, contributing to sustainable growth.
Central Purchasing body	National			Estonian Innovation Procurement Competence Centre is a supporting partner for public sector to help identify innovative ideas and bring these ideas to life through innovative procurement.
Other	National			“La French Tech” is a unique movement bringing together startups, investors, policymakers and community builders. It offers a variety of programs and services by startup-friendly ministries, regulators and public organizations to meet the needs of entrepreneurs.

2. Innovation Supply

Innovation Supply stakeholder type*	Application field of their innovation relevant for PROCEDIN*	Short description of the innovation proposed* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in PROCEDIN)
SME (Micro < 10)	Green mobility	developing fuel saving engine technology
SME (Small < 50)	Green mobility	develops, manufactures and sells heating systems for vehicles and other applications. The increasing pressure for more efficient and greener heating systems encouraged Kabola to develop Kabola Blue Ecoline (KB Eco) series.
SME (Small < 50)	Green mobility	hyperloop technology provier. To achieve net zero by 2050, they believe global hyperloop network is an indispensable . They enable convenient and sustainable high-speed transportation for everyone with the global hyperloop network
Incubator/Accelerator	Green mobility	working on all-electric flight with zero emissions
SME (Medium-sized < 250 Emp)	Green mobility	Wokring in electrification of transport. Develops, designs and manufactures battery storage solutions covering the entire technology chain from cells to pack solutions for Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) and Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), as well as energy storage solutions for utilities, grid operators and other large scale energy storage applications.
SME (Medium-sized < 250 Emp)	Green mobility	worked on an innovative, fully electric road striper for outdoor use offering low operating costs, high operational performance, zero emissions and zero vibration, so it can contribute to enhancing road safety.

3. Multipliers

Multiplier stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	Short description of their activity*
Advisors/consultancy/legal	National	Procurio provides public procurement services for both the public and private sectors. It specializes in electronic public procurement, the electronicization of public procurement processes as well as the optimization of public procurement management in the organization.
Advisors/consultancy/legal	National	Dutch public procurement expertise centre. It was set up to professionalise procurement and tendering in all government departments, with a view to improving efficiency and compliance with the rules.
Advisors/consultancy/legal	National	Estonian Innovation Procurement Competence Centre is a supporting partner for public sector to help identify innovative ideas and bring these ideas to life through innovative procurement.
Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)		The Ecosystems Foundation is an organization specializing in strategies, programs, actions and tools for sustainable development, leader in GPP and green purchasing
Associations/Lobby	National	protect the common interests of the Bulgarian municipalities, maintain and develop local self-government of the Republic and local democracy in Bulgaria.
Associations/Lobby	National	gathering the efforts of the Bulgarian municipalities for achieving a better energy efficiency and finding solutions for important national tasks
National center for Public Administration training	National	Nevi is a Dutch knowledge network for procurement, contract and supply management. They are committed to raising the purchasing profession to a higher level for individuals, organizations and society.
National center for Public Administration training	National	CIPS, the Chartered Institute of Procurement & Supply. As the awarding body for the profession they lead in education and training. Helping professionals advance their ambition. They provide insights, information and tools.
National center for Public Administration training	National	The Association for Supply Chain Management, Procurement and Logistics (BME) is the professional association for procurers, supply chain and logistics managers in Germany, and one of the largest such associations in Europe.
National center for Public Administration training	National	The purpose of the Finnish Association of Purchasing and Logistics (LOGY) is to develop procedures for purchasing of materials and services and to promote physical logistics (i.e. transport, storage, handling) and the professional skills of employees in logistics for the benefit of the Finnish economy and society.

4. Projects

Ongoing/C oncluded O/C	Relevant for collaboration Y/N/M (Maybe)	Project Acronym	Full name	Area	Domain	Type
O	Y	BUILD	Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities	innovation procurement		CSA (Network)
O	Y	InnoFacilitator	Health Innofacilitator the European Facilitator Community Promoting Public Procurement of Innovation in Healthcare	innovation procurement	health	
O	Y	PROTECT	Preparing a Pre-Commercial Procurement for end-user services based on environmental observation in the area of climate change adaptation and mitigation	innovation procurement	climate change, earth observation	CSA (Network)
O	M	CircularPSP	Public Service Platforms for Circular, Innovative and Resilient Municipalities through PCP	PCP	circular economy	
O	Y	InnoBuyer	Fast track to innovation procurement			
O	Y	CITIES 4.0	Climate Innovation Through Interactive Ecosystem Summits			
C	Y	Procure2Innovate	European network of competence centres for innovation procurement		competence centers	CSA (Network)
C	M	AI4Cities	AI accelerating Cities transition to carbon neutrality	PCP	artificial intelligence, carbon neutrality of cities	PCP
O		iProcureNet	Innovation by developing a European Procurer Networking for security research services	public procurement	security services	CSA (Network)
	Y	EAFIP	The European Assistance for Innovation Procurement			
		HAePPI				
O	Y	PRECIUS	Procurement Educational Consortium for Innovation-sourcing Using Sustainability	public procurement	Innovation	Erasmus+
C	N	E+ PERSIST				Erasmus+
O	M	EXPERTISE	Experienced Purchasers Education Research Transfer for Industry 4.0 Skills Expertise	Private purchasing and supply management / procurement skills in the digital age (private sector)	Industry 4.0	Erasmus+